

Gambling Harms in Doncaster

An evidence based briefing paper

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1. Introduction

Background

Gambling is defined as risking something of value, most often money, on an event with an uncertain outcome. The Gambling Act (2005) outlines gambling as gaming, betting, or participating in a lottery, often in the hope of winning money or a prize. Gambling is a common feature for many people in the United Kingdom, with approximately half of the adult population (48%) participating in some form of gambling. However, this decreases by approximately 50% when lottery draws are excluded (Gambling Commission, 2024).

As with other harmful products, gambling has the potential to cause direct harm to anybody who engages in gambling at any time. However, it is well documented that gambling products are connected to varying levels of harm, and certain population groups have a higher susceptibility to experience harm. As such, gambling exacerbates inequalities for those who are already vulnerable to socio-economic and health inequalities.

At a local authority level, councils have regulatory responsibility for land-based gambling premises and play a key role in the reduction and prevention of harm, in addition to raising awareness of gambling harms and embedding knowledge.

Gambling Harms

Gambling harms refers to the adverse impacts of gambling on the health and wellbeing of individuals, families, communities, and wider society. At an individual level harm can include financial, relationship, health, and educational or employment harms (The Royal College of Psychiatrists, 2021).

However, gambling harms often extend beyond the person that gambles. Findings from Public Health England (2021) concluded that 1 in 12 people are either directly or indirectly experiencing gambling harms. This may include family members such as partners and children, friends, or colleagues.

The economic burden of gambling is estimated at £412.9 million, with broader societal impacts on health ranging from £635 and £1,355.5 million. Combined this provides an estimated cost of £1.05 to £1.77 billion (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2023).

This is summarised in the infographic below.

Source: Health promotion resource guide for problem gambling prevention in Melbourne North¹²

Whilst anybody who engages in any form of gambling can be harmed, it is known that harms are not evenly distributed. There is now growing evidence that certain population sub-groups are at an increased risk due to targeting via social media platforms and advertising (Pitt et al. 2024), making them more susceptible to harm. These may include:

- Children and young people
- Boys and young men
- Those with other addictions (e.g., drugs, alcohol, smoking/vaping)
- Those with mental health difficulties
- Unemployed, economically inactive, low socio-economic status, or living in areas of high deprivation
- Certain ethnic groups (e.g., new migrants)
- Children of a person living with or recovering from a gambling addiction

Efforts to address gambling harms in the UK have predominantly focussed on individual behaviour. With much of the narrative focussing on “problem gambling” and individual responsibility, placing onus on the person that gambles whilst disregarding the innovative tactics, products, and practices of the sophisticated gambling industry (Thomas et al. 2023).

However, research has shown that much of the industry-led responsible gambling strategies, such as self-exclusion, exercising self-restraint and limiting gambling frequency or spending are ineffective (Clune et al. 2024). As such, the need for a population level, public health approach to prevention and harm reduction is widely recognised.

Purpose

The purpose of this paper is to:

- Review the existing national evidence base in relation to gambling and gambling harms.
- Review the emerging data in relation to gambling harms at a local level.
- Make recommendations on mitigating the response to gambling harms and protecting public health.

The findings of this paper will be used to provide ongoing support to the policies outlined within the Local Plan, specifically Policies 23 and 50.

2. National Evidence

Gambling in the UK

Gambling is now widely accessible, with operators present on most high streets and instant remote access due to the rise in online gambling since the inception of the Gambling Act 2005. The gambling industry has rapidly expanded as a result of the liberalisation of laws, deregulation, increased advertising and sponsorship, and the introduction of new products. As such, the UK now has one of the largest gambling markets, generating £15.6 billion in Gross Gambling Yield (GGY) in 2023/24.

There are many different forms of gambling activity, as outlined in the graphs below which include both in person and online participation (Gambling Commission, 2021).

In person participation

Online participation

Gambling participation

It is argued that methods to capture gambling behaviours in the UK are not comprehensive enough to fully understand the extent of gambling (Roberts et al. 2022). As a result, gambling participation is expected to be greater, with harms being relatively unknown and underreported. Consequently, a new methodology for collecting data as part of The Gambling Survey for Great Britain (GSGB) is now being used. Findings from the recent GSGB (2024) showed that gambling participation is highest for males aged 45-64 years, however the age profiles shifts when lottery draws are excluded, resulting in males aged 25-34 years having the highest gambling participation rates (Gambling Commission, 2024).

Men continue to be more likely than women to engage in gambling activities and experience gambling-related harm, with 2.2% of men and 1.0% of women scoring 3 or more on the Problem Gambling Severity Index (PGSI). The survey also found that younger adults, particularly those aged 25–34, had the highest prevalence of moderate-risk gambling at 3.5%, while the lowest rates were observed among those aged 75 and over (0.3%). Additionally, regional disparities persist, with Yorkshire & the Humber, the North East, and the North West showing higher gambling participation rates compared to London and the South (NHS England, 2025)

National support and treatment

GamCare is one of the main providers for gambling harms working across five regions: Yorkshire & the Humber, South East, East Midlands, London, and Scotland. GamCare also operates the National Gambling Helpline, which is available 24 hours a day, every day of the year.

GamCare national statistics for 2023/2024 show record high engagement, with the highest level of calls and online chats since records began:

- 55,228 target calls and chats (25% increase on 2022/23)
- 9,121 structured adult treatment sessions delivered.
- 23,577 live chats (up 24% from 2022/2023)
- 86% support for gamblers, and 14% support for affected others

- Chasing losses/wins primary reason for gambling (68%)
- Financial difficulties primary negative impact of gambling (74%)
- 42% likely to gamble due to the cost-of living crisis (compared to 6% of general population)

The main funder for GamCare is currently GambleAware, which receives direct funding from the gambling industry. The impact of industry partners and their influence on narrative, treatment, and prevention of harm is increasingly identified as a barrier to responding to gambling harms (van Schalkwyk et al. 2024; McCambridge et al. 2014). The Association of Directors of Public Health (2022) argue that the current funding system creates a conflict of interest that results in the gambling industry minimising the impact of harm, a practice seen in other industries such as tobacco, alcohol, fossil fuels and pharmaceuticals. With the growing recognition of funding implications, NHS England ended the dual commissioning and funding arrangement with GambleAware in 2022, due to the conflict of interest in resources provided by the gambling industry.

In 2024, NHS England reached its target outlined in the NHS Long Term Plan (2019) to provide 15 specialist treatment centres for gambling through eight regional services, in line with action on prevention and health inequalities. These centres provide a wide range of services including clinical assessments, psychological therapies (such as CBT), and psychiatric support for co-occurring mental health issues. They also offer peer and family support, personalised care plans, and help with financial and social challenges. Access is open to individuals aged 13 and over via self-referral or through professionals (NHS England, 2024) . Referrals to these clinics have gone up almost 130% in April to September 2024 compared to the same period in 2023 (NHS England, 2024).

In November 2024, the Department for Culture, Media and Sport confirmed the statutory levy on gambling operators which will aim to raise £90-£100million annually to improve the provision of high-quality, independent research on gambling. 50% of the funding will directly benefit NHS-led gambling treatment. 20% will be allocated to UK Research and Innovation and the Gambling Commission to direct further research. 30% will be used to develop a comprehensive approach to prevention of harm and early intervention, however further consideration is currently being given to appoint an appropriate body to lead this approach.

Gambling and the Economy

Total gross gambling yield (GGY) of the Great Britain Gambling industry for the period April 2023 – March 2024 was £15.6 billion, an increase of 3.5% on the previous year, and 10.2% increase pre-lockdown period. GGY is the amount retained by operators from customer stakes after the payment of winnings, but before the deduction of costs of the operation.

The total GGY for Land-based Sectors (arcades, betting, bingo, and casino) for the same period was £4.6 billion, an increase of 3.8% on the previous year, despite a 0.8% decline in the number of premises nationally. In England, betting shops account for the majority of land-based products. This is mirrored in Doncaster, with 44 betting offices (out of a total 54 licensed gambling premises).

Research from the National Centre for Social Research (2021) has shown that 86% of GGY was generated from just 5% of customers who experience the highest spending losses. Furthermore, industry data from betting firms show that just 2% of customers yield 83% of deposits, as a result of VIP schemes that aim to increase gambling participation. Further data also outlines how those experiencing harm are nine times more likely to be offered incentives to continue gambling such as free bets or bonus offers (Gambling Commission, 2023).

The Department for Culture, Media & Sport (2023) estimate that the gross value added (GVA) by the Gambling sector was £5 billion in 2022. GVA by the Gambling sector grew faster than the UK economy as a whole, increasing by 45% between 2010 – 2019 compared to 18% for the UK economy. However, Corfe et al. (2021) argue that the gambling industry has a significantly lower benefit on the economy compared to other services such as retail, or food and beverage services due to the limited supply chain, and lack of job creation.

The Royal Society for Public Health developed a Richter Scale of Health to measure healthiness of shops on the high street. Health impacts were scored based on four areas of health: Healthy/Healthier Choices, Social Interaction, Access to Services and Advice, and Mental Wellbeing. Bookmakers were classified as the 2nd most unhealthy outlet for high streets, following High Cost Credit Outlets.

3. The local context and challenges for the City of Doncaster

There has been unprecedented growth in commercial gambling and online access in recent years, alongside sophisticated marketing, advertising, and sponsorship. Other harmful commodities and addictions, such as tobacco and alcohol, are widely recognised in public perception and reflected in national strategy and policy. However, gambling and the commercial determinants of health are a relatively novel area of public health in comparison.

Commercial determinants refer to the private sector activities that influence health, particularly the conditions, actions, and omissions of commercial actors (WHO, 2023). Commercial determinants also impact health equity by shaping social, economic, and political systems, as well as influencing finance and investment flows. Furthermore, a lack of understanding or widespread misconceptions about the gambling landscape in the UK may perpetuate stigma, creating barriers to accessing support and openly discussing gambling harms. However, despite historically limited epidemiological data of gambling harms at local levels, emerging data is now available in Doncaster.

Gambling licensed premises in Doncaster

In Doncaster, there are approximately 263 different gambling licensed premises at present. This includes 54 licensed gambling premises comprising of 44 betting offices, seven adult gaming centres, three bingo premises, and two tracks (one horse racing and one greyhound racing). These premises are predominantly located around the city centre, and within communities that have high levels of deprivation.

Pubs and other alcohol licensed premises are automatically entitled to two category C or D gaming machines. Licensing authorities can also issue gaming machine permits which allow

additional machines. In Doncaster there are 165 Gaming Machine Alcohol Premises with a further 16 gaming machine permits.

Club gaming or machine permits are available to members' clubs, miners' welfare institutions and commercial clubs, this permits equal chance gaming such as poker and bingo, as well as up to three gaming machines in total of categories B3A, B4, C or D. In Doncaster there are 28 club permits in total.

The Gambling Commission provides further information on gaming machine categories [Gaming machine categories \(gamblingcommission.gov.uk\)](https://www.gamblingcommission.gov.uk).

The health profile of Doncaster

The health of people in Doncaster is generally worse than the England average. Life expectancy for both men (76.9 years) and women (81.4years) are lower than the England average (79.3 years and 83.2 years).

At a local level, life expectancy for men is 10.9 years lower, and 8.2 years lower for women, in the most deprived areas of Doncaster compared to the least deprived areas, demonstrating health inequalities.

In England, Healthy Life Expectancy (HLE) has been steady for a number of years, however rates in Doncaster have been falling since 2015-2017 for both males and females. As a result, Doncaster now reports some of the worst HLE data in the country.

Location of gambling premises and rates of participation in Doncaster by deprivation indicators

It is known that the highest rates of gambling participation are among people who have higher academic qualifications, people who are employed and among relatively less deprived groups. However, the socio-demographic profile of those who gamble appears to change as gambling risk increases, with harm being associated with people who are unemployed and living in more deprived areas, suggesting that gambling harms are related to health inequalities (Office for Health Improvement & Disparities, 2023).

Doncaster is the 4th most deprived area in the Yorkshire and Humber region. In Doncaster, one third of residents live in the 20% most deprived areas nationally, this equates to approximately 129,000 people living in areas with the highest deprivation levels in England. Furthermore, an estimated 1 in 4 children in Doncaster live in relative low income families, equating to approximately 14,666 children, compared to 1 in 5 in England (Office for National Statistics, 2024).

Research has evidenced how a higher proportion of gambling premises are located within areas of high deprivation, with 21% of premises within the most deprived deciles compared to 2% within the least deprived (Evans and Cross, 2021). As a result, gambling exposure and behaviours are normalised within populations that face greater inequalities. The infographics below show the distribution of betting shops in Doncaster alongside levels of deprivation. The accompanying graph shows the percentage of the population living in each ward in Doncaster that reside within 1km of a betting shop.

% population Within 1km of a Betting Shops

Key

Betting Shops	Deprivation
Betting Shop	IMDDec
1km Buffer	1
Wards	2
	3
	4
	5
	6
	7
	8
	9
	10

Gambling participation in Doncaster

Analysis from Public Health England (2019) shows the prevalence of gambling participation by upper tier local authority (UTLA).

Overall, 19 UTLAs had a gambling participation rate that is statistically higher than average for England. Doncaster was among those with the highest participation rate, ranking 10th out of a total 119 UTLAs.

Estimates of treatment and support needs in Doncaster

Research conducted by the Office for Health Improvement and Disparities (2023) produced estimates of the number of adults who gamble in England that might benefit from treatment or support. It also estimated the number of children living in the same household as adults who might benefit from some type of gambling treatment or support.

Support and treatment were grouped into five types based on the level of intervention, ranging from one to five. The table below shows the total number of adults and children in Doncaster who might benefit from some form of treatment or support for gambling.

Treatment or support intensity	Adults in Doncaster	Children in Doncaster
(1) brief advice	909	552
(2) extended brief advice	5512	3361
(3) psychological interventions delivered in the third sector	1014	645
(4) psychologist-led cognitive behavioural therapy	1610	1019
(5) intensive residential treatment	248	136

At present, a GamCare commissioned service is the only treatment or support service in Doncaster for Gambling. The NHS Northern Gambling Service for the Yorkshire region have clinics located in Sheffield and Leeds.

Local service provision

Between 1st October 2023 and 30th June 2024 there were 44 referrals to NECA, the GamCare commissioned service in Doncaster. Over half of those accessing the service were male (59.1%), with the majority being the person that gambles (rather than affected others). Almost two thirds (63.6%) of attendees were aged under 34 years. This can be seen in the infographic below.

The leading type of harm experienced by Doncaster residents were Anxiety/Stress (22.4%) and Financial Difficulties (22.4%), followed by Family/Relationship Difficulties (17.6%) and Depression/Low Mood (15.2%). Furthermore, 6.4% reported Suicidal History (Thoughts/Plans/Attempts) and/or Current Suicidal Thoughts.

The most common type of gambling activity was Online Casino (slots) followed by Gaming Machines (Fixed Odds Betting Terminals) in Bookmakers and Online Betting Exchange.

At ward level, the highest prevalence of residents accessing the service appeared to be related to areas experiencing high levels of deprivation. The Stainforth & Barnby Dun ward and Wheatley Hills & Intake ward had the highest prevalence. Followed by Hexthorpe & Balby North, Thorne & Moorends and Finningley wards.

Gambling harms and behaviour in Doncaster's children and young people

The Pupil Lifestyle Survey has been developed by the City of Doncaster Council's Public Health Department in conjunction with independent research agency, PFA Research.

Results from the school year 2023/2024 attempt to show an understanding of young people's behaviour locally in relation to gambling. Data is representative of pupils in Doncaster in year groups 8 and 10. The results of the survey show that participation in gambling is steadily increasing year on year.

- 61% of pupils take part in one or more gambling activities, at least occasionally.
- 67% play arcade games for fun and 22% play arcade games to win money.
- Approximately 1 in 5 have tried to win their money back (15%) with 11% reporting that they have/do find it hard to stop gambling.
- Across almost all settings boys have a higher tendency than girls to engage in gambling activities at least once a month.
- 18% of pupils have bought loot boxes when playing online games, this was significantly higher in boys than girls (27% v. 7%).
- Boys are more likely to show signs of addictive behaviours than girls (26% v. 18%).
- SEN pupils have a higher propensity to play games of chance or gamble than pupils overall, as well as taking part in all suggested gambling activities at least once a month.
- 32% of young carers play arcade games for fun, the highest observation across the cohorts.
- 45% of pupils say they would know where to go if they or someone they know might have a gambling problem. Boys are more likely to know where to get help than girls (50% and 40% respectively).
- Pupils from an Ethnic Minority Group were least likely to know where to go if they or someone they know might have a gambling problem.
- Young carers were more likely to buy lottery tickets, play games to make money and engage with gambling for money. They were also most likely to know where to go for help with gambling problems.

Education and support for children and young people in Doncaster

The Young Gamers and Gamblers Education Trust (YGAM) is a charity that provides education to young people to inform, educate, safeguard, and build resilience, helping them to make informed decisions and understand the consequences around gambling and gaming. In November 2023, YGAM delivered a University and Student Engagement Programme to over 550 students at Doncaster College. Findings from the programme highlighted that 96 young people (17.2%) have gambled with their own money in the past 12 months, the highest prevalence was amongst those aged 16 years.

Evaluation following the programme showed:

- 25.5% increase in understanding why people might game and/or gamble.
- 15.3% increase in understanding the financial risks of gaming and gambling.
- 19.6% increase in understanding how gaming or gambling might affect health and wellbeing.
- 25.5% increase in understanding how gaming or gambling can impact others.

- 33.3% increase in understanding where to go for support if worried about themselves or others.

Gambling and Suicide in Doncaster

Suicide is complex and most often many factors or events can lead someone to take their own life. However, there is an established link between gambling addiction and suicide attempts and ideation, and it is estimated that between 240 and 700 people take their own life every year in England related to gambling (Public Health England, 2021). As a result, gambling is now outlined in the National Suicide Prevention Strategy 2023-2028.

Analysis from the Office for Health Improvement and Disparities (2023) suggests that deaths from suicide were significantly higher among adults experiencing direct gambling harm compared to the general adult population. Further research also demonstrates how young people (aged 24 years and under) that have experienced gambling addiction were more likely to attempt suicide. This was 9 times higher for men and 5 times higher for women (Wardle & McManus, 2021).

The suicide rate in Doncaster is significantly higher than the England average. This is illustrated in the graph below which shows the number of deaths in Doncaster per 100,000 compared to the England rate.

4. Role of planning, licensing, and enforcement powers to address gambling harms

In accordance with the Gambling Act 2005, City of Doncaster Council carries out its licensing functions with a view to promoting the following three licensing objectives which are central to the regulatory regime created by the Act -

1. Preventing gambling from being a source of crime or disorder, being associated with crime or disorder, or being used to support crime.
2. Ensuring that gambling is carried out in a fair and open way.
3. Protecting children and other vulnerable persons from being harmed or exploited by gambling.

The Statement of Licensing Policy is under review for 2025-2028. Currently, the Director of Public Health is consulted on any application for a new license. Public Health complete a risk profile of the area and submit it to the licensing department for consideration as part of the application process. It should be noted the Licensing Authority (City of Doncaster Council) is not involved in licensing remote gambling, which is regulated by the Gambling Commission via operating licences.

The Gambling Act (2005) places a legal duty on the licensing authority to aim to permit gambling. As a result, the licensing authority must approach their functions in a way that seeks to regulate gambling by using measures such as conditions to licenses to moderate the impacts on the licensing objectives. This requires a whole council approach that draws upon various departments and partners. Where intelligence is received that licensees may be allowing those that are under the legal age of 18 years to gamble, the premises is inspected and reminded of their obligations under their licence. If intelligence is received of continued failures, test purchasing can be used to evidence non-compliance. However, unlike alcohol or drug use which can lead to anti-social behaviour and cause public nuisance, the harms associated with gambling are often not visible, and local intelligence is lacking.

Planning

Since 2021 there have been eight planning applications for gambling premises submitted to the City of Doncaster Council as the licensing authority. 7/8 were approved with the exception being one, that was refused on the grounds of contributing to proliferation and overconcentration in a close proximity, in accordance with Policy 23 of the Local Plan. Several authorities have seen increases in applications to open 24-hour gambling premises on high streets, particularly within the past 12 months (Ahmed 2024; Dale and Gregory 2024; Gerrard 2024). In December 2022, Buzz Bingo submitted a planning application to extend operating hours to 24-hour, all days of the week. The application was approved in May 2023.

5. Policy

Local Policy

The Doncaster Local Plan sets out policies and proposals to meet Doncaster's need for housing, employment, and other development. Policy 23: Development within Town, District and Local Centres outlines proposals to change the use to a Betting Shop, Amusement Arcades, Pay Day Loan Units and Pawnbrokers. Policy 50: Health outlines how the council will improve and promote strong, vibrant, and healthy communities by ensuring a high quality environment is provided with local services to support health, social, and cultural wellbeing.

Doncaster Delivering Together (2020-2030) is a 10-year strategy that emphasises the need to improve wellbeing through six wellbeing goals. This includes building a fair and inclusive city by reducing inequalities, including a reduction in the number of areas in Doncaster that fall within England's 10% most deprived communities. It also highlights the vision for safe and resilient communities that improves the safeguarding of vulnerable children and adults.

The Doncaster Health and Wellbeing Strategy is currently under review.

National Policy

Promoting health is explicitly stated in the National Planning Policy Guidance (NPPG) and identifies that planning policies and decisions should aim to achieve healthy, inclusive, and safe places that enable and support healthy lifestyles, especially where this would address identified local health and well-being needs. The NPPG goes on to describe a healthy place as one which supports and promotes healthy behaviours and environments, and a reduction of health inequalities for people of all ages. It also stipulates that planning can influence the built environment to improve health in local communities. Planning policies, where justified, seek to limit the proliferation of particular uses where evidence demonstrates and in doing so, evidence and guidance produced by local public health colleagues and Health and Wellbeing Boards may be relevant.

6. Recommendations

Preventable ill health stemming from unhealthy commodities including gambling undermines productivity, life chances, financial security, and impacts on child health and development. All of which exacerbates health inequalities and creates cycles of disadvantage, whilst also placing unnecessary burden on public infrastructure including health and social care.

The multi-agency Gambling and Financial Inclusion Group continues to co-ordinate an appropriate and targeted action plan for Doncaster, utilising the Public Health Framework for Preventing and Reducing Gambling Harms in Yorkshire & Humber, developed by the Yorkshire and Humber Association of Directors of Public Health. Mitigation interventions and measures to prevent gambling harms in Doncaster include the following recommendations:

Supply Reduction Strategies -

- Deter proliferation of gambling venues in town and local centres by **Restricting Gambling Venues and Licenses**, particularly in communities identified as vulnerable to experiencing harm through local data and intelligence.
- Utilise planning powers at a local level to **Limit Gambling Venue Hours of Operation**.
- **Enforcement of Legal Age Operation** by increasing inspections of venues and enacting penalties through test purchasing operations.

Demand Reduction Strategies -

- **Restricting Advertising** through council owned services and continue to support the need for national policy that can be universally applied to wider settings, including through the South Yorkshire Mayoral Combined Authority.
- Facilitate health promotion through **Information and Awareness Campaigns** via community focused websites such as Your Life Doncaster and St Leger Homes.
- Work with local businesses and organisations to **Disseminate Harm Prevention Messaging** to employees at varying levels including management and human resources.

Risk Reduction Strategies -

- **Foster Collaboration between Gambling Support Services and Suicide Prevention Networks** by ensuring mutual referral pathways for individuals at risk of suicide or those experiencing gambling harms.
- **Prohibiting Gambling Venues in Vulnerable Populations** by working with stakeholders and elected members, utilising local data and intelligence.
- Promote awareness across pub trades to encourage **Alcohol Bans/Restrictions** in venues where gambling machines and alcohol consumption are readily available.

Harm Reduction Strategies -

- Facilitate **Gambling Harms Training** for frontline staff that focuses on opening the conversation about gambling harms and signposting to treatment or service pathways.
- Encourage **Tests and Screening** to support professionals to identify individuals who may be experiencing gambling harm in conjunction with other issues such as debt, mental health, or suicidal thoughts/attempts.
- Ensure that **Helplines, Information and Support Services** are available in gambling premises in locations that are both prominent and discreet. This includes access to the NHS Northern Gambling Service for treatment, as well as other gambling and mental health support.

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